

Interlaminar Defect Criticality for Compressive Loading

R. B. Pipes¹⁾, J. D. Webster²⁾, W. A. Dick¹⁾

- 1) Center for Composite Materials, University of Delaware, 208 Evans Hall, Newark, DE 19711, U.S.A.
2) Hercules, Inc., P.O. Box 98 (Mail Stop 2343T), Magna, UT 84044, U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

Inherent material flaws in composite laminates may result in substantial performance loss. The complex nature of this strength loss is influenced by several parameters including loading, laminate stacking sequence and thickness, flaw size, and defect type. These various effects have not, however been fully characterized and hence there exists a need for establishing flaw criticality data.

Both analytical and experimental studies are performed to investigate the compressive behavior of graphite/epoxy laminates containing delamination defects. Interlaminar disbands in these composites may result from a myriad of processing faults, poor handling technique, inadequate process conditions, or may arise as a function of hard particle impact damage [1, 2]. Delaminations are simulated by insertion of Kapton or Teflon film between plies of the graphite/epoxy laminates, and the flaw criticality is measured by residual strength results. The compressive buckling behavior of laminates containing circular delaminations is modeled analytically with excellent agreement with experimental results.

Two experimental programs are described: i) sandwich beam compression testing performed under four point flexure [3-5] and ii) direct in-plane compression using the IITRI test technique [6]. Circular and elliptical disbands, as well as, simulated delaminations resulting from lamina ply drops, are examined in the experimental work. The sandwich beam testing examines several laminate stacking sequences and investigates the effect of disband location through the thickness of the graphite/epoxy composite [7, 8]. Six, eight, and twelve ply laminates are subjected to loading, with synthetic defects implanted either at the mid or quarter depth planes. A total of five stacking sequences are studied, including $[0/\pm 45]_{2s}$, $[0/\pm 45]_s$, $[90/\pm 45]_s$, $[\pm 45]_{2s}$, and $[0/\pm 45_2/0]_s$ for the compressive surface, with unidirectional facesheets on the tensile side. Direct compression (IITRI) tests are performed on 36-ply laminates with the stacking sequence $[0/\pm 45]_6$. These tests examine localized near-surface buckling of the composite; circular and oblong teflon film disbands are implanted at locations three and six plies below the free surface. Ultrasonic inspection of all samples is performed to indicate the extent and nature of the damage propagating from the delamination site. Additionally, local strain is

monitored with electrical resistance (strain) gages to establish the onset of buckling near the implanted disbond.

The analytical model employs the Raleigh-Ritz solution method of the anisotropic laminate containing a circular disbond and undergoing uniaxial compression to determine the critical buckling loads. The Raleigh-Ritz method involves selecting an expression for the out-of plane deflection, then computing the potential energy expression. The integration is carried out and the variation is taken with respect to the unknown amplitude coefficients. This yields approximate results for the critical buckling load, whose accuracy is dependent on the accuracy of the assumed form of deflection [9, 10]. The analytical values determined in this manner are shown to compare quite favorably to those measured in the experimental work [11].

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